

INDIA'S POSITION ON REFUGEES AND THE PRINCIPLE OF NON-REFOULEMENT: CASE OF ROHINGYA REFUGEES IN THE COUNTRY

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Abstract

What is India's position on refugee settlement inside its territory? What does it think of the principle of non-refoulement? What importance does the country accord to the international legal standards in this regard? These are some of the departing questions of this research paper. An important case in this regard is that of Mohammad Salimullah versus the Union of India (2021) which concerns the deportation of Rohingyas from India. The paper argues that India presents a case of selective generosity and discriminates amongst the refugees on the basis of their religion while granting them refuge and citizenship rights in the country. It also emphasises that India has reflected an arbitrary stance on the principle of non-refoulement. The author cites the above stated case along with two others to prove the argument.

As such, adopting the approach of case analysis, the paper begins with a short introduction to the landscape of refugees in India. It moves on to review some literature that informs the author's arguments and moves on to later sections in which the relevant cases have been presented and analysed. The paper concludes with some conspicuous conclusions that can be drawn from the study while advocating for the legislation of a distinct refugee law in India.

Keywords: Refugees, Rohingya Refugees, UNHCR, non-refoulement

Introduction:

The current international order has prompted a sharp increase in the number of refugees around the world. A UNHCR report brought out around mid-2024 estimated the number of forcibly displaced people to

be 122.6 million worldwide, of which an estimated number of 37.9 million were refugees. (UNHCR, 2023) This leads us to our first question- Who are refugees?

The United Nations Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees 1951 or the Convention on Refugees is a key legal document that governs the entire refugee regime globally. It defines the term 'refugee' as follows:

“As a result of events occurring before January 1951 and owing to well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country; or who, not having a nationality and being outside the country of his former habitual residence as a result of such events, is unable or, owing to such fear is unwilling to return to it.” (UNHCR, 1951, p.14)

As such, non-refoulement becomes a core principle of the Convention. Article 33(1) of the Convention describes the principle as follows:

“No Contracting State shall expel or return (“refouler”) a refugee in any manner whatsoever to the frontiers of territories where his life or freedom would be threatened on account of his race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion.” (UNHCR, 1951, p.30)

Thus, this principle bars the nation-states from deporting a refugee back to his/her country where he/she runs high the risk of being persecuted on the basis of fundamental grounds such as race, religion, etc. Albeit this principle is an intrinsic part of the Convention and obliges the “Contracting State”, it nevertheless is a part of several other international instruments as well such as International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) 1966, Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC) 1989, etc. Thus, any country which is a part of such international conventions/treaties is bounded by the principle of ‘non-refoulement’, irrespective of the fact if it is a party to the Refugee Convention or not. Moreover, the UNHCR Executive Committee has endorsed it as *jus cogens*; it binds states irrespective of their acceptance to a particular treaty, and any action that contravenes *jus cogens* is void (Hossain, 2005). India's Gujarat High Court had also said, “There is substantial, if not conclusive, authority that the principle is binding on

all states, independently of specific assent.” (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.08)

“India is one of the most prominent refugee receiving countries in the world. According to Refugee International estimates, India hosts around 3,30,000 refugees” (Bhattacharjee, 2008, p.71). However, in the absence of any distinct Refugee Law, India’s position on the acceptance of refugees has been ambiguous. This has subjected refugees to “ad-hoc administrative measures” (Alexander, 2021, p.115). For example, while the State has adopted repressive measures against Rohingyas entering India through the land borders the country shares with Bangladesh, Chakmas- another minority community belonging to East Pakistan (now Bangladesh) have been well accepted in the country. The Government of India, in fact, went ahead with granting citizenship rights to tens of thousands of Chakmas. At this point, let us take a look at who these minority communities are.

Rohingyas:

According to a report by the UNHCR (2024), Rohingyas are “the most persecuted minority in the world”. They are Muslim refugees belonging to the State of Buddhist Myanmar who “have faced institutionalised discrimination, such as exclusionary citizenship laws”, at least since 1948 (Albert & Maizland, 2020). In 1982, the country amended its Citizenship Law and refused to recognise them as its citizens altogether, thus, effectively rendering them Stateless. A large-scale violence broke out in Rakhine state- home to “the majority of the estimated one million Rohingya in Myanmar” (Albert & Maizland, 2020) and a mass exodus of the community ensued. Since then, there have been multiple waves of displacement, the largest of which was brought about in August 2017. It forced “more than 742,000 people- half of them children- to seek refuge in Bangladesh.” (UNHCR, 2024). A significant number of them have also been seeking refuge in countries like India, Malaysia, Thailand, etc. According to a UNHCR report dated August 22, 2024, India has an estimated number of 93,100 Rohingyas in the country. This crisis has pushed the community to the edges, rendering them extremely vulnerable to exploitation, sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV), and abuse (USA for UNHCR, 2024).

Chakmas:

A report by The Hindu (2021) informs, “the Chakmas and Hajongs are ethnic people who lived in the Chittagong Hill Tracts, most of which are located in Bangladesh. Chakmas are predominantly Buddhists, while Hajongs are Hindus.”. Their migration to India from East Pakistan began in 1964 as a result of their loss of land to the development of Kaptai Dam on the Karnaphuli River. The report also says that “they also faced religious persecution as they were non-Muslims and did not speak Bengali. They eventually sought asylum in India. The Indian government set up relief camps in Arunachal Pradesh and a majority of them continue to live there even after five decades.” (The Hindu, 2021)

In short, Chakmas were the refugees from East Pakistan. They immigrated into India, and eventually settled in Arunachal Pradesh. The Government of India, subsequently endowed citizenship rights to them in accordance with Article 5(1) (a) of the Citizenship Act, 1955.

Evidently, the country's policy viz. accepting refugees in India has not been consistent. While the State accepted and granted citizenship rights to the Buddhist Chakmas coming into India from East Pakistan, Rohingyas- originally of Myanmar origin and Muslims by religion, who immigrated into India through Bangladesh, have historically been denied refuge. Hence, it can well be argued that the country has adopted a discriminatory nature while granting citizenship rights to ethnic entering India from its neighbouring countries and have established religion as the basis of that discrimination.

This paper delves further into the issue and analyses India's position on the matter by taking into account three court cases, namely:

- i) Mohd. Salimullah versus the Union of India (2017)
- ii) Ktaer Abbas Habib Al Qutaifi versus Union Of India (1998)
- iii) Committee for Citizenship Rights of the Chakmas of Arunachal Pradesh versus the State of Arunachal Pradesh (2015)

The paper shall also take into account various acts and sections of the Indian Constitution that govern the acceptance (or rejection thereof) of refugees into India.

Literature Review:

To understand the case of refugees in India, having a theoretical framework that explains the perception of refugees in the broader field of international migration is pertinent.

Jeremy Hein (1993) discusses a realist versus nominalist debate on the status of refugees. He informs that “refugee crises are a consequence of the political dynamics of state formation and transformation, and of increasing global interdependence”. He goes on to say, “Like immigrants, refugees organise migration through social networks, but the composition of their networks and the effects of migration on social identity differ.” (Hein, 1993) Paradoxically, however, “analysis of western refugee policy supports the nominalist perspective because who is or is not admitted as a refugee remains closely tied to foreign policy interests.” (Hein, 1993)

In understanding India’s position on the acceptance of refugees, a study conducted by Ashish Bose in 2003 sheds some light. Bose, in his study, analysed the situation of Afghan refugees in India. On the basis of the same, he observed that there were almost 10,000 Afghan refugees in India during that time, belonging mostly to Sikh and Hindu community (Bose, 2004). He said that “most of their efforts to become Indian citizens are a cry in the wilderness thanks to the bureaucratic hurdles and the absence of a Refugee Law in India.” (Bose, 2004, p.4701) However, he presented a case of the spokesman of the Afghan Sikh refugees in India, Manohar Singh, who managed to get a citizenship. Interestingly, he also presented a case of one of the Muslim Afghan refugees who “in spite of his efforts, he has not been given Indian citizenship, though he wants to be in India.” (Bose, 2004, p.4701). The author also says that “the UNHCR felt that Hindu and Sikh refugees from Afghanistan were fairly well integrated in Indian society and there was no urge on their part to go back to Afghanistan.” (Bose, 2004, p.4699) Although this statement does not contain any explicit observation on the discriminating nature of the Indian state on religious grounds while granting citizenship to the Afghan refugees, the same can be inferred from the article upon close observation. The absence of any observation by the UNHCR on the granting of citizenship to the Muslim Afghan refugees could have been the result of the embedded censorship in the Indian administrative framework.

Professor Ghoshal (2017) also sheds important light on the issue of refugees in India. In regard to Rohingyas in India, he says, “India's response to the Rohingya issue is calibrated on an understanding of the history and complexities of Myanmar's politics of ethnicity and legitimacy.” (Ghoshal, 2017, p.03). He provides an insight into the militant activities of Rohingyas in Myanmar and argues that it is the problematic connections of the Rohingyas with terrorist organisations that have been worrisome for the Indian State, pertaining to which it has been reluctant in accepting Rohingyas as refugees. However, “New Delhi has to balance between its security concerns and moralism on humanitarian issues”, (Ghoshal, 2017, p.03) he says.

The following section delves into the cases in order to infer India's official stance on the position of refugees in India.

Case I: Mohd. Salimullah v. the Union of India Case (2021)

On August 8, 2017, the Government of India, by means of a letter, directed all the State governments and Union Territory administrations “to sensitise all the law enforcement and intelligence agencies for taking prompt steps and initiating deportation processes” (Supreme Court of India, 2021, p.02) of the Rohingya refugees in India. This prompted two petitioners- Mohammad Salimullah and Mohammad Shaqir, the Rohingya refugees from Myanmar, to file a writ petition with the Supreme court demanding:

- i) the release of the Rohingya refugees from the sub-jail in Jammu
- ii) a direction to the Union of India not to deport the Rohingya refugees who have been detained in the sub-jail in Jammu

The petitioners had invoked the principle of non-refoulement and said that the same is guaranteed under Article 21 of the Indian constitution. They had contended that Article 14 which guarantees equality before law was also relevant, and that Article 14 as well as Article 21 were also available to non-citizens. Articles 14 and 21 of the Indian constitution read as follows:

Art. 14 Equality before law- The State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India.

Art. 21 Protection of life and personal liberty- No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law. (Government of India, 2024)

Moreover, the two petitioners also pointed out that though India is not a signatory to the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol, it is a party to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966, the Convention on the Rights of the Child 1992, the Protection of All Persons against Enforced Disappearances, and the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment. Thus, the principle of non-refoulement was a binding obligation for India.

In response, the Union of India invoked the Foreigners Act of the Indian Constitution and said that the people for whom protection is being asked are foreigners (Section 2a) and the Central Government, empowered by Section 3 of the Act, reserves the right “to issue orders for prohibiting, regulating or restricting the entries of foreigners into India or their departure therefrom.” (Supreme Court of India, 2021, p.04). Section 2(a), Section 3 of the Foreigners Act read as follows:

Section 2 Definitions:

- (a) “foreigner” means a person who is not a citizen of India; Section 3 Power to make orders
- (1) The Central Government may by order make provision, either generally or with respect to all foreigners or with respect to any particular foreigner or any prescribed class or description of foreigner, for prohibiting, regulating or restricting the entry of foreigners into [India] or their departure therefrom or their presence or continued presence therein. (Government of India, 2018)

In response to the petitioners’ contention that Articles 14 and 21 are available to non-citizens, the Union of India said that Article 19(1) (e), which accords the fundamental right to reside and settle in the country is available only to the citizens of the country. Art. 19(1)(e) of the Constitution reads as follows:

Section 19(1)(e) Protection of certain rights regarding freedom of speech, etc.- All citizens shall have the right to reside and settle in any part of the territory of India. (Government of India, 2024)

The Respondent further emphasised that given India is not a part of the 1951 Convention on Refugees and its 1967 Protocol, the obligation of compliance with the same does not fall upon India, as the principle of non-refoulement is applicable only to the “Contracting State”. The ‘Doctrine of Precedent’ was also invoked by the Respondent to argue that the petition should be dismissed as the Court had dismissed a similar application that challenged the deportation of Rohingyas from the State of Assam on October 4, 2018. An emphasis was also laid on *Gambia v. Myanmar* adjudicated by the International Court of Justice on January 23, 2020. To this, the respondent argued on the basis of the principle of sovereignty and said that the same has no relevance to the present application as “the Union of India generally follows the procedure of notifying the Government of the country of origin of the foreigners and order their deportation only when confirmed by the Government of the country of origin that the persons concerned are citizens/nationals of that country and that they are entitled to come back.” (Supreme Court of India, 2021, p.05)

The main issues that the Respondent cited due to which they thought the Rohingyas should be deported are as follows:

- i. Illegal migration: Due to open/porous Indian land borders that it shares with many countries, a continuous threat of an influx of illegal migrants persists. Further, this influx is organised and well-orchestrated through various agents and touts for monetary considerations.
- ii. National security: The influx of illegal migrants poses serious national security ramifications, an opinion well compounded by the intelligence agencies who raised serious concerns about the same.

The Court adjudicated in favour of the Respondent and said that the interim relief prayed for by the Petitioners could not be provided.

Case II: Ktaer Abbas Habib Al Qutaifi versus Union Of India (1998)

In this case, the petitioners Mr. Ktaer Abbas Habib Al Qutaifi and Taer Al Mansoori, both of Iraq origin, sought direction from the Gujarat High Court, by way of Special Civil Application, to release them from detention at the Joint Investigation Centre, Bhuj, District Kutch, State of Gujarat. They requested that instead of deporting them to Iraq, they may be handed over to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) on the principle of non-refoulement.

The Petitioners brought their petition in front of the Court on grounds that they feared persecution in their country, if deported. They had cited Iraq's Decree No. 115 dated August 25, 1994 which stipulated "cutting off one auricle of one ear of a person in event of non-performance of military service, deserting from military service or shouldering or protecting anyone who has evaded or deserted from military services. The decree further stipulates that a horizontal line shall be tattooed on the forehead of person whose ear has been cut off." (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.01) Since the Petitioners did not want to join the Army due to their "abhorrence of violence" (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.01), they feared persecution by State upon their return to their country.

The observations of the Court in this case attracts interest. In its order, the Court allowed the Special Civil Application and directed the Respondent to consider the Petitioners' request from "humanitarian point of view" (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.10). Following statements were made by the Court:

- i) "The International Conventions and Treaties are not as such enforceable by the Government, nor they give cause of action to any party, but there is an obligation on the Government to respect them." (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.09)
- ii) "The work of the UNHCR being humanitarian, on certification of Refugee, the Government of India is under obligation to ensure that Refugees receive international protection until their problem is solved." (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.09)
- iii) "In view of directives under Article 51(c) and Article 253, international law and treaty obligations are to be respected. The Courts may apply those principles in domestic law, provided such principles are not inconsistent with domestic law." (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.09)

Case III: Committee for Citizenship Rights of the Chakmas of Arunachal Pradesh (CCRC) versus the State of Arunachal Pradesh (2015)

In CCRC versus the State of Arunachal Pradesh (2015), the petitioner-CCRC sought direction against the Union of India to grant citizenship to the Chakma and Hajong Tribals who migrated to India in 1964-1969 from East Pakistan (now Bangladesh) and settled in the state of

Arunachal Pradesh. The Supreme Court, in this case, protected the rights of the Chakmas and directed the Government of India and the State of Arunachal Pradesh to confer citizenship to the eligible Chakmas. The order also asked the authorities to ensure the community's protection of life and liberty and against any discrimination (Supreme Court of India, 2015). As noted above, the Chakmas were the refugees from East Pakistan, who had lost their land to the development of Kaptai Dam on the Karnaphuli River and had immigrated into India during 1964-69.

This case serves as an effective precedent for the acceptance of refugees in the country; and until the State discriminates amongst refugees on the basis of their religion, Rohingyas- an ethnic, Muslim minority from Myanmar should have been accepted into the country in the likely manner.

The following section has been divided into two parts. While the first discusses key legal provisions relevant to accepting (and granting citizenship to) refugees in India, the second evaluates and critically analyse the three cases cited above. The objective is to gauge India's stance on refugees and the principle of non-refoulement.

Key Legal Provisions Governing India's Refugee Regime

In India, there are primarily two Acts that govern refugees in India.

1. The Foreigners Act 1946 (last amended on December 3, 2018)

Following sections of the Foreigners Act are often quoted by the parties involved in cases that concern refugees and immigrants:

Article 2 Definitions:

- a) "foreigner" means a person who is not a citizen of India; (Government of India, 2018)

Article 3 Power to make orders:

- 1) The Central Government may by order make provision, either generally or with respect to all foreigners or with respect to any particular foreigner or any prescribed class or description of foreigner, for prohibiting, regulating or restricting the entry of foreigners into India or their departure therefrom or their presence or continued presence therein. (Government of India, 2018)

2. The Citizenship Act 1955

In regard to this Act, two sections become relevant while granting citizenship to the migrants in India.

Section 5 Citizenship by Registration:

(1) Subject to the provisions of this section and such other conditions and restrictions as may be prescribed, the Central Government may, on an application made in this behalf, register as a citizen of India any person not being an illegal migrant who is not already such citizen by virtue of the Constitution or of any other provision of this Act if he belongs to any of the following categories, namely:-

- i) a person of Indian origin who is ordinarily resident in India for seven years before making an application for registration; (Government of India, 1955)

Section 2(1) (b): defines an “Illegal Migrant” as a foreigner who has entered into India-

- ii) without a valid passport or other travel documents and such other document or authority as may be prescribed by or under any law in the behalf; or
- iii) with a valid passport or other travel documents and such other document or authority as may be prescribed by or under any law in that behalf but remains therein beyond the permitted period of time; (Government of India, 1955)

However recently, in 2019, the Government of India took a controversial step and made an amendment to the Citizenship Act 1955. According to the Citizenship Amendment Act 2019, the following proviso shall be inserted in the section 2(1) (b):

"Provided that any person belonging to Hindu, Sikh, Buddhist, Jain, Parsi or Christian community from Afghanistan, Bangladesh or Pakistan, who entered into India on or before the 31st day of December, 2014 and who has been exempted by the Central Government by or under clause (c) of sub-section (2) of section 3 of the Passport (Entry into India) Act, 1920 or from the application of the provisions of the Foreigners Act, 1946 or any rule or order made

thereunder, shall not be treated as illegal migrant for the purposes of this Act;" (The Gazette of India, 2019, p.02)

This amendment to the Citizenship Act 1955 is problematic as it establishes religion as one of the criteria for the Indian State to grant citizenship to the refugees in India. "Before the CAA, India's citizenship law did not make religion a determinant of a person's eligibility for an Indian passport. All those seeking naturalisation had to show that they were in India legally, and needed to wait for the same period – 11 years – to become eligible for citizenship." (Al Jazeera, 2024). However, the CAA changes this. Now, people who identify themselves as Muslims, running from "well-founded fear of persecution" in their home countries, such as Rohingyas from Myanmar, "will still need to wait for 11 years before they become eligible for Indian citizenship. And unlike Hindus, Parsis, Sikhs, Buddhists, Jains and Christians, they need valid documentation to justify their presence in India." (Al Jazeera, 2024) Indeed, this problematic amendment to the Citizenship Act has come under a lot of flak by the international community as well as the scholars of international migration, who are criticising the Indian government for establishing discriminatory grounds amongst the refugees.

Analysis of the Court's orders in the 3 Cases:

Ad hoc interpretation of non-refoulement: The Court's adjudications in the cases cited above are a clear example of the ad hoc nature of the Indian judiciary in matters concerning refugees in India. The Supreme Court of India, in its ruling in Case I cited above, ruled that although Article 21 (along with Article 14) is available to non-citizens as well, it added that the right not to be deported, is ancillary or concomitant to Article 19(1)(e), thereby, renouncing the principle of non-refoulement, and ordering the deportation of thousands of Rohingya refugees. This stands in stark contrast to the ruling of the Gujarat High Court which, in its ruling in Case II, had observed "the principle of 'non-refoulement' is encompassed in Article 21 of the Constitution" (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.09) and hence, ordered the authorities to consider the application from the "humanitarian point of view" (Gujarat High Court, 1998, p.10). The Court had stalled the Petitioners' deportation.

Problem with the invocation of Art. 19(1) (e) of the Indian Constitution: As noted in Case I, the Respondent invoked Art. 19(1) (e) in its contention against the Petitioners and said that the absolute right to

reside and settle in the country is accorded by Art. 19(1) (e), but the same is available only to the citizens of the country; the fact that the petitioners are identified as foreigners under Section 2(a) of the Foreigners Act means that the law does not apply to them. The Court, as it turned out, agreed with the contention. However, it is imperative to note that Article 19 of the Indian constitution relates to the “Protection of certain rights regarding freedom of speech, etc.” (Government of India, 2024). It is in this regard that Section 1 of the same enumerates rights available to the citizens of the country, while in the concerned case, Freedom of speech had no relatability whatsoever. Thus, the Court could have made the Respondent’s contention inadmissible. In not doing so and accepting the same, the Indian judiciary laid bare the country’s position on refugees.

Doctrine of Precedent and the Conclusion therefrom: In Case I, the Respondent had invoked the Doctrine of Precedent to argue that that the court should dismiss the petition as it had earlier dismissed a similar application that challenged the deportation of Rohingyas from the State of Assam. There existed other precedents, the acceptance of Chakma refugees being one of the most appropriate ones, that the Indian judiciary could have invoked to rebut the Respondent’s arguments. The Court, instead, ordered the deportation of Rohingya refugees which leads one to establish that the Indian state has adopted a discriminatory attitude on religious grounds during the process of accepting refugees in its territory. The observation gains grounds when one notices it in the light of the CAA 2019.

Gaps between Indian court rulings and its international law obligations: In Case I, the SCI had pointed out that a prominent issue in front of it was “whether Article 51(c) of the Constitution can be pressed into service.” (Supreme Court of India, 2021) Article 51(c) of the COI which reads as follows:

Promotion of international peace and security- The State shall endeavour to- foster respect for international law and treaty obligations in the dealings of organised peoples with one another; (Government of India, 2024)

comes under the Directive Principles of State Policy. However, as long as it does not conflict with India’s municipal law, it can be applied in word and spirit (Alexander, 2021). It is indeed evident that the

contended obligation in the article is the “treaty obligations”, however, to observe that non-refoulement is a customary international law that transcends the treaty commitments, is also important. The fact that India decided to deport Rohingyas is reflective of the gap between Indian domestic court rulings and its international law obligations. This should also be considered in light of the fact that India, though not party to the 1951 Refugee Convention, is a signatory of several other international instruments including International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) 1966, Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC) 1989, etc.

Conclusion

The most important conclusions that can be drawn from the above study are as follows:

- i) India has an arbitrary take on non-refoulement
- ii) India practices religious discrimination while accepting refugees in its territory

India's ad hoc nature while adjudicating on non-refoulement is well evident when one compares the court's rulings in two cases namely, *Ktaer Abbas Habib Al Qutaifi versus Union of India* (1998), and *Mohd. Salimullah versus Union of India* (2021). While in the former, the Court recognised that non-refoulement was encompassed in Article 21 of the Constitution and effectively had stalled the deportation of the Iraqi Petitioners, in the latter, it had renounced non-refoulement and had ordered deportation of Rohingya refugees.

Moreover, the Indian state's religious bigotry in accepting refugees is well evident in the recent amendments it did to the Citizenship Act 1955. However, it comes as no surprise as the same is merely an extension of what the State has been practising. It had accepted Chakmas- Buddhist minorities from East Pakistan (now Bangladesh) during 1964-1969 and granted them citizenship rights, but had chosen to deport Rohingyas- a Muslim minority belonging to the State of Myanmar.

It is pertinent now that India has a dualist approach when it comes to its policies in regard to the acceptance of refugees inside its territory. One can note that until India has a separate domestic legislation incorporating the legal obligations of the international instruments it is party to, it

cannot be bound by the obligations of the same. Hence, in light of the looming humanitarian crises of current times, it is highly important that India adopts a distinct Refugee Law. By doing so, India shall emerge as a leader in South Asia by projecting itself as a responsible power responding to the region's needs. It shall also stand true to its philosophy of 'Vasudhaiv Kutumbakam', i.e. the universality of mankind as one family', quite literally!

References:

1. Albert, E., & Maizland, L. (2020). The Rohingya Crisis. *Council on Foreign Relations*. <https://www.cfr.org/background/rohingya-crisis>
2. Alexander, M. A. (2021). *Critical Analysis of Mohammad Salimullah v. Union of India: Has the Supreme Court of India acted as Executive?* 3(1). <https://www.cmr.edu.in/school-of-legal-studies/journal/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/06-Critical-Analysis-of-Mohammad-Salimullah-v-Union-of-India-Has-the-Supreme-Court-of-India-acted-as-Executive.pdf>
3. Bhattacharjee, S. (2008). India Needs a Refugee Law. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 43(9), 71–75.
4. Bose, A. (2004). Afghan Refugees in India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 39(43), 4698–4701.
5. Committee For C.R.Of C.A.P. & Ors vs State Of Arunachal Pradesh & Ors on 17 September, 2015 (Supreme Court of India 2015). <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/163542302/>
6. Ghoshal, B. (2017). India's Responses to the Complex Rohingya Crisis in Myanmar. *East - West Center*. https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/resrep17388.pdf?refreqid=fastly-default%3A97c12f1a1e9eba9e2d716c85d24561bd&ab_segments=0%2Fbasic_search_gsv%2Fcontrol&initiator=&acceptTC=1
7. Government of, I. (n.d.). *The Citizenship Act, 1955*. <https://thc.nic.in/Central%20Governmental%20Acts/Citizenship%20Act,%201955..pdf>
8. Government of, I. (2018). *THE FOREIGNERS ACT, 1946 (Modified as on 3rd December, 2018)*. <https://www.indiacode.nic.in/bitstream/123456789/2259/3/A1946-31.pdf>
9. Government of, I. (2019). *The Gazette of India*. https://indiancitizenshiponline.nic.in/Documents/UserGuide/E-gazette_2019_20122019.pdf

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10. Government of, I. (2024). *THE CONSTITUTION OF INDIA [As on 1st May, 2024]* 2024. MINISTRY OF LAW AND JUSTICE, Government of India.
<https://cdnbbsr.s3waas.gov.in/s380537a945c7aaa788ccfcdf1b99b5d8f/uploads/2024/07/20240716890312078.pdf>
11. Hein, J. (1993). Refugees, Immigrants, and the State. *Annual Reviews*, 19, 43–59.
12. Hossain, K. (2005). The Concept of Jus Cogens and the Obligation Under The U.N. Charter. *Santa Clara Journal of International Law*, 3(1).
<https://digitalcommons.law.scu.edu/scujil/vol3/iss1/3/>
13. INTERLOCUTORY APPLICATION NO.38048 OF 202 IN WRIT PETITION (CIVIL) NO.793 OF 2017 MOHAMMAD SALIMULLAH AND ANR. Petitioner(s) VERSUS UNION OF INDIA AND ORS. Respondent(s) (Supreme Court of India 2021).
<https://indiankanoon.org/doc/10486034/>
14. Ktaer Abbas Habib Al Qutaifi And Anr. vs Union Of India (Uoi) And Ors. on 12 October, 1998 (Gujarat High Court 1998).
<https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1593094/>
15. UNHCR. (n.d.). *GLOBAL TRENDS FORCED DISPLACEMENT IN 2023*.
<https://www.unhcr.org/global-trends-report-2023>
16. UNHCR. (1951). *Convention and Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees*.
<https://www.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/legacy-pdf/3b66c2aa10.pdf>
17. UNHCR. (2024). *Rohingya Refugee Crisis Explained*.
<https://www.unrefugees.org/news/rohingya-refugee-crisis-explained/>
18. Who are Chakmas? (2021). *The Hindu*.
<https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/who-are-chakmas/article61473775.ece>
19. Why is India's Citizenship Amendment Act so controversial? (2024). *Al Jazeera*.
<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2024/3/12/why-is-indias-citizenship-amendment-act-so-controversial>